

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

Reference: 101087984

Co-funded by
the European Union

HerStory Fine Tuning Transnational Report

WP4 D4.2

HerStory Consortium

Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Author	Modification
1	0	11/09/2024	Marilena Stathopoulou	First version
2	0	18/10/2024	Marilena Stathopoulou	Second version
2	1	14/03/2025	Alicia García Holgado	To fix grammar issues and match the numbers with the real data

HerStory - Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies is a project funded under European Union Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values (CERV) Programme (Ref. 101087984). The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of contents

1.	Introduction	1
2.	Methodology of evaluating the Pilot excursion tours	1
3.	Evaluation of the Pilot excursion tours.....	2
4.	Reccomentations for improvement HerStory tour	4
5.	Conclusion.....	6
5.1	Salamanca, Spain	7
5.2	Fort-de-France, Martinique	7
5.3	Nicosia, Cyprus.....	8
5.4	Athens, Greece.....	8
5.5	Velenje, Slovenia.....	9
5.6	Vilnius, Lithuania	9
5.7	Lecco, Italy	10
6	Annex.....	10
6.1	ANNEX 1: HerStory EXCURSION TOUR survey results	10

1. Introduction

The HerStory Map tour was implemented by all participants in eight cities — Salamanca, Nicosia, Sofia, Martinique, Vilnius, Athens, Lecco, and Velenje — exploring monuments dedicated to important women in each city’s history. The implementation of the tours took place between May and August 2024, with a total of 178 participants, including 121 young people from various fields such as humanities, politics, arts, education, journalism, anthropology, and others. In addition, stakeholders included professionals from sectors such as education, diversity and inclusion, history, and other individuals interested in learning more about women’s contributions to urban history.

Taking into account the specific characteristics of each city, the partners designed dedicated tours to create a unique experience for all participants while raising awareness of the historical footprint left by the women featured in the HerStory Map. All partners have analysed the elements of their local HerStory tours and included them in the HerStory Tour Guidelines, which are available on the HerStory website with open access.

An important element of the pilot tour excursions was the evaluation of each national tour by participants, providing insights to support the development of the final HerStory Map tour. A summary of the evaluation and key areas for improvement is analysed in the following chapters of this document.

2. Methodology of evaluating the Pilot excursion tours

For the evaluation of the excursion tours, all participants were invited to provide anonymous feedback through the official EU survey for events organised under the CERV programme. A total of **120 responses** were collected across all participating countries, reflecting participants’ experiences and insights gained during the pilot implementation.

In addition, the survey provided valuable information regarding participants’ knowledge of EU laws, initiatives, and national legislation. While the majority of participants demonstrated awareness of rights and legislation at both the European and national levels, their familiarity with specific EU initiatives — such as EU Roma Week, Access City Award, Equal Pay Day, European Disability Card, and the European Citizens’ Initiative — was comparatively lower.

Participants also completed the [HerStory survey](#), which focused on specific aspects of the tour's implementation, including their awareness of women's contributions to the city's history, the activities conducted during the tour, interactions with local communities, and factors such as the distances between monuments, the variety of activities, the locations visited, and the performance of tour guides. [ANNEX 1]

3. Evaluation of the Pilot excursion tours

The feedback received for all eight tours was overwhelmingly positive, indicating that all partners successfully met the initial objectives. Participants across all cities where the HerStory tour was conducted demonstrated a notable increase in knowledge regarding the significant contributions of women in history. It was evident that there was a general lack of awareness about the impactful roles played by women. Additionally, all participants acknowledged that the HerStory tour contributed to promoting gender equality and ensuring equal opportunities for all, leading to an enhanced understanding of these important issues.

The activity in **Salamanca, Spain** received positive feedback, particularly for offering participants the opportunity to explore the city while learning about its history, engaging with peers, and participating in the Quizizz game. The distances between points were deemed appropriate, and participants actively engaged, with some sharing their knowledge of various locations, enhancing the experience during transitions. Participants also provided valuable suggestions for improving the overall experience.

In **Fort-de-France, Martinique**, participants enjoyed visiting five key locations. While some of the young women were familiar with certain sites, most were unfamiliar with the places visited. Few concerns raised was the walking distance between locations, (approx. 10 to 15 min), since Martinique has a car-centric culture and hot climate it was a challenge by tour guide to provide answers in some participants historical questions about the women. The engaging elements of the tour were the interactive questions, the hints, and the group discussions while two-thirds of participants felt inspired to further explore women's history, and nearly all expressed interest in visiting more monuments on the HerStory map.

In **Nicosia, Cyprus**, across six locations, the overall feedback from participants in both pilot excursions (one for young people and one for stakeholders) was highly positive. Stakeholders

and young participants expressed their appreciation for the HerStory project and its objectives, emphasizing the widespread lack of knowledge and information about significant female historical figures in European cities, particularly in Cyprus and Nicosia.

In **Athens, Greece** the HerStory tour was implemented in five spots in the city center. Overall, the tour received positive feedback, effectively raising awareness of women's contributions to Greek and Athenian history. Participants gained new perspectives, though the information they received of women's role in Greek history, highlighting a potential gap in their education on the topic. Engaging activities such as interactive questions and personal connections with figures of the local community enhanced the experience. While the tour's structure, including monument distance, was well-received, suggestions for improving activity variety, pacing, and tour guide interaction emerged. Participants expressed strong interest in further exploring women's historical contributions, showcasing the potential for continued engagement with the HerStory initiative.

In **Sofia, Bulgaria** 13 locations, Nevertheless, the tour was quite successful and lively. The distance and time period were found normal and adequate by both groups. About a quarter of all participants shared willingness for a more continuous tour or exploring more map locations on their own.

The tour in **Velenje, Slovenia**, which covered three locations, was well-received and sparked significant interest among participants, especially the introductory meeting, which outlined the HerStory project, provided participants with a clear understanding of their role. The use quiz games used after each location enhanced engagement, particularly among younger participants. Due to distance there was a need to drive between locations, however this seemed not to affect participants' enthusiasm and maintained their engagement as they had time for discussions about the women featured on the tour and the importance of gender equality. Notably, the youngest participants were unfamiliar with the women highlighted, such as Jelka Reichman and Alma Karlin, but were eager to learn about them.

The pilot tour in **Vilnius, Lithuania**, was successful, with the active participation of students while receiving the information. Many were introduced to notable women, whose contributions were previously unknown to them. The accessible locations allowed for comfortable group discussions, and students particularly enjoyed finding locations using

hints, walking through the city, and engaging with the guide. Most found the walking distance adequate, and highlighted the balance between the number of activities and tour length could enhance the experience. While interest in further exploring the historical impact of women was moderate, there was strong enthusiasm for discovering more monuments on the HerStory map. Overall, feedback was positive, with the interactive nature of the tour being a highlight.

The excursion in **Lecco, Italy**, was successfully highlighted the lack of awareness regarding regional female contributors in the city, underscoring the importance of recognizing women's contributions across various spheres and appreciating the opportunity to learn about significant local women and their stories. The engaging treasure hunt format made the experience interactive and enjoyable, fostering enthusiasm and collaboration among participants. Additionally, poor internet connectivity in some areas hindered adherence to the planned itinerary. However, some participants faced challenges locating certain stops, found some segments less compelling, and expressed a desire for more hands-on activities. One limitation noted regarding the necessity of transportation between various points, though it also provided an opportunity to explore the region more comprehensively, unveiling previously unseen perspectives.

4. Recommendations for improvement HerStory tour

A crucial aspect of the HerStory tour was the valuable feedback participants provided regarding specific areas for improvement. This input not only highlighted participants' experiences but also identified opportunities to enhance future interactions in the implementation of the final tour.

Feedback from participants in the HerStory tour in **Salamanca** highlighted several key areas for improvement. Managing distractions, such as side conversations and group members falling behind during the activity, emerged. However, participants demonstrated strong re-engagement when stories of significant women were shared, indicating that effective storytelling effectively captured their attention. Participants expressed a desire for a longer tour duration, as the current length felt too short and requested more comprehensive information about each woman featured at every stop along the route, requesting the leaflets

that contained complete details about all points on the map to be distributed at the beginning to accompany the tour. Enhancements in the quality of guides and activities were recommended, including the incorporation of more interactive elements that do not rely on smartphones and the addition of more points of interest to enrich the experience. Additionally, logistical concerns regarding the meeting points were raised, addressing various weather condition.

In **Martinique**, the development of a digital booklet accessible after the tour could enhance participants' engagement by providing additional historical information about the women and locations featured. This booklet could take the form of a straightforward digital version of the text prepared by the tour guide during the event, supplemented with further explanations and relevant links for deeper exploration.

To enhance the HerStory tour experience in **Nicosia**, participants recommended to involve more experts during the tour and enrich the interactive components while provide deeper insights. Additionally, expanding the tour to include more locations around the city would further enhance the mapping experience. The high engaged audience also recommended the establishment of a communication network to set up collaborations with local authorities that will strengthen community engagement and organise regular gatherings with stakeholders to exchange ideas and best practices. To ensure the sustainability of the HerStory map it was recommended to conduct regular updates post-project completion as this is crucial for its ongoing relevance. Finally, incorporating all cities in Cyprus and collaborating with all European partner countries will help to broaden knowledge, improve information dissemination, and increase the overall impact of the initiative.

In **Athens, Greece**, participants recommended to extend the time spent at each monument to facilitate a more thorough exploration and appreciation of women's significance in each field. Additionally, to develop a wider variety of activities at each site that would enrich the overall experience. Participants also emphasized the importance of refining the tour guide's role to include more storytelling, which would enhance the narrative aspect of the tour. Finally, improving the integration of local community interactions is crucial for fostering a deeper connection between participants and the historical context of the visited sites.

In **Sofia, Bulgaria**, it was recommended to take into consideration the weather conditions on tour days, and other variables in the design phase. Furthermore, the development of specialized thematic tours tailored to specific interests. These could include dedicated tours highlighting Bulgarian women in various fields, such as science, social activism, and the arts and poetry.

In **Velenje, Slovenia**, the group recognized the importance of including another notable female figure, Urška Stropnik Šonc, a distinguished fine arts professor and accomplished illustrator, in the HerStory online map and accompanying guidelines. Additionally, to consider weather conditions and transportation between monuments as critical factors while designing the final tour. These locations are accessible via public transport, such as buses and trains, therefore promoting the use of public transportation is recommended to enhance sustainability in future excursions.

In **Vilnius, Lithuania**, participants indicated a strong interest in incorporating more activities centered on women's contributions. However, from the guide's perspective, many students seemed fatigued after one hour, indicating a need to balance the number of activities with the overall duration of the tour. Moreover, it is advisable to consider the walking pace of participants and to adjust the tour length or add additional sites accordingly.

In **Lecco, Italy**, participants expressed curiosity regarding the future of the HerStory map, specifically about its maintenance and potential updates with the inclusion of new female figures. Participants suggested enhancing the experience by including more biographical details and personal anecdotes about the women featured during the treasure hunt. Additionally, introducing rewards or recognition for those who complete the tasks more quickly could further motivate and engage participants.

5. Conclusion

The insights provided by participants offer significant added value to the development of the final HerStory tour that is planned from September 2024 to November 2024. They highlight critical areas for enhancing engagement, such as improved storytelling, thematic tours, and the inclusion of more biographical details. Recommendations for logistical improvements, like balancing tour length, managing distractions, and adapting to weather conditions, ensure a

smoother and more enjoyable experience. Additionally, the feedback emphasizes sustainability, with suggestions for digital resources, expanded locations, and collaboration with local authorities, all of which will contribute to a richer, more dynamic, and impactful final tour. Each partner city will update the final HerStory experience based on the knowledge acquired, aiming to create an impactful and inspiring presentation of women in each city's history.

The specific recommendations per city are summarised below:

5.1 Salamanca, Spain

- Extend the duration of the tour to allow participants more time to fully engage with the content and locations.
- Provide detailed information about each woman featured at every stop, either through on-site storytelling or supplementary materials.
- Distribute leaflets containing comprehensive information at the beginning of the tour, allowing participants to reference them throughout the activity, rather than waiting until the end.
- Enhance guide quality and incorporate more interactive activities that do not rely on cell phones, making the experience more immersive.
- Add more points of interest along the tour route to enrich the educational experience.
- Plan the tour for inclement weather by selecting a covered or indoor location for the final gathering and the prize-giving ceremony, such as a university cafeteria or other sheltered spaces, ensuring a comfortable and smooth conclusion regardless of conditions.

5.2 Fort-de-France, Martinique

- Adjust the pace and plan for tours with diverse age groups, taking into consideration the distances and the transportation among monuments, to enhance comfort.
- Improve guide preparation and ensure tour guides are thoroughly briefed on all historical figures and locations to better address participant questions.
- Enhance educational materials with the development of a digital booklet with additional historical information about the women and locations that are featured in

the tour. Include expanded details, links, and further reading suggestions to encourage continued learning after the tour.

5.3 Nicosia, Cyprus

6. Update the tour plan based on seasonal weather patterns, and provide necessary comforts especially on heatwaves.
 - Adjustment of the route plan and walking speed considering the audience needs, the weather conditions, the sidewalks and streets to ensure safety and comfort.
 - Review and ensure accuracy of information provided for all the points on the map.
 - Collaboration with a professional guide during the tour, to deliver essential information without overwhelming participants, improving the overall educational and immersive quality of the tour.
 - Combine a treasure hunt game with the actual tour and allow the group to discuss as they walk between tour stops to make the interactions during the tour more engaging and fun.
 - Share a small booklet with participants, that includes detailed information on all the points identified on the map and give the opportunity to explore the information at their own pace and deepen their understanding.
 - Add more significant locations to the HerStory map, enhancing the richness of the tour experience.
 - Ensure map sustainability with regular updates of HerStory map.
 - Establish partnerships with local government and authorities to support the ongoing communication and development of the tour.
 - Host regular stakeholder meetings with stakeholders to exchange best practices, share ideas, and discuss improvements for future tours.

5.4 Athens, Greece

- Enhance the tour's duration at each monument to allow more in-depth exploration and reflection on women's contributions.
- Incorporate a wider range of interactive activities at each monument to make the experience more dynamic and engaging.

- Encourage guides to focus more on storytelling, providing untold stories and historical insights that keep the interest of the participants.
- Consider minor adjustments to the walking route or pacing to ensure the monument spacing remains comfortable for all participants.
- Integrate more opportunities for participants to engage with local community elements, enhancing the connection to the surrounding context and culture.
- Expand the tour to include women from a variety of fields and time periods to diversify the representation of historical contributions.

5.5 Velenje, Slovenia

- Improve pre-tour preparation with an introduction of the program and HerStory tour before the tour starts, to ensure participants have a clear understanding of the HerStory project and expectations
- Include Urška Stropnik Šonc, a notable local artist and illustrator, on the HerStory map and in the tour guidelines to highlight her contributions.
- Provide recommendation on transportation for distant locations (e.g., Šoštanj, Celje) to reduce the walking time, especially during heatwaves.
- Encourage the use of public transportation (bus, train) for future tours to promote sustainability.
- Move the Kahoot quiz to the end of the tour and conduct it indoors (classroom or café) to avoid IT challenges, ensuring participants have stable WiFi and proper equipment.
- Offer a small prize for the quiz winner to further motivate participation.

5.6 Vilnius, Lithuania

- Limit the number of activities to prevent participant fatigue, especially when the tour exceeds one hour.
- Incorporate activities to keep participants engaged without overwhelming them. (e.g., storytelling, interactive discussions, or short hands-on tasks).
- Plan the tour route according to the average walking speed of participants, ensuring a comfortable pace for everyone.

5.7 Lecco, Italy

- Regularly update the HerStory Map to include more local women and their contributions, ensuring that new figures are consistently integrated into the tour narrative.
- Use local landmarks or place names to further connect participants with historical figures and emphasize their significance in the community.
- Consider organizing transport or guided driving routes for future tours to enhance accessibility while still allowing participants to appreciate the local landscape.
- Address poor internet connectivity issues by providing printed materials or offline resources that participants can access all stops that are available at the map.
- Include more hands-on activities or interactive elements during the tour to keep participants engaged and to enhance their learning experience.
- Include more biographical details or personal anecdotes stories about the women that are included at the treasure hunt.
- Consider introducing rewards or recognition for participants who complete tasks quickly or engage actively during the tour, such as small prizes or certificates

6 Annex

6.1 ANNEX 1: [HerStory EXCURSION TOUR survey results](#)

1. Which city tour did you attended? (0 βαθμός)

Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες

Πληροφορίες

● Athens	8
● Lecco	8
● Martinique	15
● Nicosia	2
● Salamanca	0
● Sofia	20
● Velenje	18
● Vilnius	17
● Άλλο	1

2. Which are the fields that women have been succesful in history? (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

● Science	19
● Art	45
● Politics	28
● Sports	10
● Academics	36
● Health	25
● All	38

3. Women 's impact to your city history is well known. (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

● Strongly disagree	11
● Disagree	46
● Neutral	23
● Agree	8
● Strongly agree	1

4. Which activity of the excursion did you find most engaging? (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

76
Απαντήσεις

Πιο πρόσφατες απαντήσεις
"All"

10 ερωτηθέντες (13%) απάντησαν **women** για την ερώτηση αυτή.

5. Whas the distance among monuments well designed to provide a pleasant tour experience? (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

4.33

Μέση αξιολόγηση

6. Please select your opinion regarding the tour distance (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

- The distance was good 73
- Long distance between some m... 12
- Long distance between most of ... 4
- The distance is too short betwe... 0

7. Which aspects of the excursion can be improved or be different? (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

- *Locations* 10
- *Tourguide* 8
- *Activities* 31
- *Duration* 18
- *Other* 23

8. We would love to read your recommendation on how to improve: (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

52
Απαντήσεις

Πιο πρόσφατες απαντήσεις

"The Tour was really nice. I highlighted locations since I imagine that more symbolic places relate...

"The tour was perfect"

[Ενημέρωση](#)

8 ερωτηθέντες (15%) απάντησαν **Več kvizov** για την ερώτηση αυτή.

9. Did you had any interaction with local elements (information about surroundings, meeting locals, having any activity involving local community, or other) ? (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

- Yes 75
- No 14

10. If NO, would you like to add interaction with local elements? (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

10
Απαντήσεις

Πιο πρόσφατες απαντήσεις

"Yes, as written above it might be nice an interaction with someone telling stories, opening the d..."

[Ενημέρωση](#)

3 ερωτηθέντες (25%) απάντησαν **No** για την ερώτηση αυτή.

11. At which extent did the excursion inspire you to explore further into the topic of women in history? (1=lowest, 5= highest) (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

1 -Not at all	3
2- Slightly	5
3- Moderately	31
4- Very Much	34
5- Extremely	16

12. Are you willing to explore more monuments on the HERSTORY MAP? (0 βαθμός)

[Περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες](#)

[Πληροφορίες](#)

Yes	66
No	2
Maybe	21

